

A Digital Mathematics Learning Support Centre Based on a Curated German-Language Collection of Mathematical STACK Problems

Gozel Judakova¹, Oleg Boruch Ioffe², Lisa König³, Reik V. Donner⁴

Abstract: Abstract: Mathematical STACK problems with automated feedback offer students digital opportunities to consolidate their mathematical skills anywhere and anytime. During the winter term 2022/23, our team has started systematically integrating weekly digital problems and regular e-assessments into the curricular mathematics courses for civil engineers at the Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences. Monitoring and statistical analysis of students' usage behaviour and learning success have been complemented by two structured surveys during the teaching period. The obtained results provide the basis for further improvements of the general course design and specific integration scenario of STACK problems into the curricular mathematics courses in different engineering programs.

Keywords: Mathematics for Civil Engineers, STACK problems with automated feedback, e-assessments.

1 Introduction

Digital learning materials provide students with a tool for reducing individual knowledge deficits especially in basic courses like Engineering Mathematics without being strictly tied to the time and place of the corresponding lectures. During the recent Covid-19 pandemic, emergency remote teaching [Ho20]; [Bo21] has boosted the amount of digital learning and teaching materials that have often been developed in an ad-hoc manner [Er21]. With careful curation and didactic embedding, such materials provide a treasure for sustainably improving teaching quality at universities worldwide by complementing classical teaching and learning scenarios with digital self-study and learning support materials.

¹ Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences, Breitscheidstraße 2, Magdeburg, D-39114
oleg-boruch.ioffe@h2.de

² Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences, Breitscheidstraße 2, Magdeburg, D-39114
gozel.judakova@h2.de

³ Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences, Breitscheidstraße 2, Magdeburg, D-39114
lisa.koenig@h2.de

⁴ Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences, Breitscheidstraße 2, Magdeburg, D-39114
reik.donner@h2.de

To account for the rising demand for digital self-study materials in Mathematics and support both students and lecturers in their digital education scenarios during the pandemic, Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences has recently established a digital Mathematics Learning Support Centre as part of the learning management system Moodle. Its first version was originally developed on rather short notice during spring/summer 2020 to respond to emerging needs during the first phase of the pandemic and has been based on an existing and gradually expanded in-house collection of digital problems implemented with the commercial software WIRIS/CalcMe [Do23]. Given the practical limitations found with this approach, we are currently establishing an improved course design based on Moodle quizzes incorporating STACK problems. For this purpose, many existing German-language mathematics exercises already implemented in STACK have been collected among the German STACK community and have been carefully classified and partially revised, including the removal of duplicate problems and addition of detailed solutions where missing as an initial feedback level. A more systematic implementation of detailed feedback trees is planned as a part of future work.

To date, the revision of the currently established collection has mainly focused on the curricular topics of the Mathematics 1 (basic concepts, linear algebra, and analytical geometry) course for Civil Engineers. In this course, selected mathematical STACK problems have already been used as the basis for weekly digital self-assessments and voluntary intermediate e-assessments of the students during the past winter term 2022/23. A further expansion towards the Mathematics 2 (real-valued one-variable calculus) and 3 (real-valued multivariate calculus, numerical methods, and statistics) contents of the Civil Engineering bachelor program is currently underway. As part of this development, we have identified a few course topics that have been underrepresented in the existing collection. These areas are currently being completed by further additions provided by the German STACK user community, German-language translations from English-language collections of STACK problems (especially for the field of statistics), and new problems developed by our own team (for example, on the solution sets of inequalities), which are to be enriched by careful integration of interactive JSXGraph visualizations.

2 Transition from WIRIS to STACK-based problems

The exploitation of digital mathematical problems for student self-study and e-assessments at Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences originally started in 2013. Prime factors motivating those early attempts have been observations of an increasing heterogeneity of the students regarding their individual educational backgrounds and initial mathematical skills along with continuously high numbers of students withdrawing from the study programs during their first year at university [Br20]. After first positive experiences with targeted support materials on elementary mathematics provided for students with special demands enrolled in the Electrical and Mechanical Engineering courses [Me14], an online pre-study course has been developed, which was first offered in winter term 2016/17 in terms of a collection of basic quizzes implemented

as part of the learning management system Moodle. At this point, the system was merely able to distinguish right from wrong solutions of the collected problems, but unable to provide a detailed response to the students about possible solutions of errors.

To account for the corresponding deficits and didactic inefficiencies, interactive mathematical problems have been developed for supporting the study entrance phase in the Electrical and Mechanical Engineering programs since the winter term 2018/19. Other than the earlier attempts, these problems were accompanied by integrated information on solution strategies, typical sources of errors, or even complete exemplary solutions. To allow for comfortable utilization by the students, problems have been encoded by the commercial CalcMe software along with the WIRIS Quizzes plugin for Moodle, with involves a graphics-based equation editor like those used in standard office software like MS Word for providing the obtained solutions as input to the system. Once commissioned, the software has also been used in other course areas like Physics, Electronics, and several others in the university's two Engineering departments. Those efforts have been further boosted by an ad-hoc digitization of mathematical problems from standard textbooks to provide our students with additional self-study and self-assessment resources during the peak phase of the Covid-19 pandemic in spring/summer 2020.

The explosive development of WIRIS based mathematical problems (at present about 450 covering a vast body of mathematical topics) and their utilization not only for self-study, but also examination purposes in the Engineering Mathematics classes however also brought several limitations and practical problems to attention (cf. Tab. 1):

- Due to the commercial nature of the software, running license costs emerge for the university. Moreover, a German-language user community was found to be practically non-existing, posing challenges to efficient support in case of arising questions during problem development and an absence of existing open educational resources that further extensions could be based upon. Developing additional digital content along with proper quality control was hence requiring strong involvement of the Mathematics teaching staff, which posed a particular challenge during the peak phase of the pandemic when emergency remote teaching needed to be developed and organized.
- When developing new digital problems in CalcMe and testing them within Moodle, the developers team encountered challenges in terms of long processing times on the server, the reasons for which could not be identified unanimously. Such processing times provided a practical problem for the further systematic expansion of the collection of problems. Moreover, it turned out that the WIRIS plugin for Moodle did not work along with the mobile Moodle app used by many students.
- Besides those mainly technical concerns, a major didactic limitation to using WIRIS based mathematical problems results from the fact that sequential errors cannot be handled (or at least only by complicated workarounds) and integrated into the automated feedback provided to the students.

The points motivated the decision in favour of a transformation to a STACK-based problem collection made in summer 2021 and continuing since. Except for the still pertaining necessity of providing input to the system by proper text-based encoding (which may pose challenges to students with low programming experience or affinity), essentially all previously raised points are properly addressed by using STACK (cf. Tab. 1 for an overview of essential properties of both systems):

- it is open-source and has a global community of developers,
- it runs smoothly along with the computer algebra system Maxima with straightforward integration into Moodle, and
- it allows for flexible feedback trees to be implemented.

Property	WIRIS Quizzes	STACK
Input of solutions	Graphical user interface	Text-based encoding
Control of correct input by user	Direct (graphics-based input)	System-generated graphical output shown before evaluation
Computation time	Slow, since GUI input is processed by Moodle as html	Relatively fast
Licensing	Commercial, license costs	Open source
Community	Small, no known German-language user groups	Large international and German-language user communities
Handling of sequential error	No automated feedback	Implementation of sequential error trees possible
Feedback to users	Only asynchronous after submission of solution	More flexibility
Equivalence reasoning	Not possible	Possible

Tab. 1: Comparison of key features of WIRIS and STACK.

3 Description of the database

The starting point for developing a curated for-purpose collection of mathematical STACK problems and Moodle quizzes based upon them have been two existing German-language databases: DOMAIN (<https://db.ak-mathe-digital.de>, Ruhr University Bochum) and DIGITALER AUFGABENPOOL MATHEMATIK (<https://aufgabenpool.th-koeln.de>, Cologne University of Applied Sciences, henceforth referred to as “Aufgabenpool” for brevity). Specifically, we have followed the curriculum of the course series Mathematic 1-3 in the Civil Engineering bachelor program of our university starting with the winter term 2022/23 to successively develop a carefully curated collection of corresponding digital learning materials that fit the contents of the corresponding courses. The associated developmental workflow comprises the following steps:

- (1) Classify all mathematical STACK problems contained in the DOMAIN database according to our course contents, and check for duplicates and proper functionality. From originally 845 problems, we thereby kept 785 as the initial database to build upon⁵.
- (2) Compare the collection of problems thus obtained with the topics of the baseline Engineering Mathematics curriculum. Whenever gaps in topical coverage are identified, check the Aufgabenpool database for corresponding suitable problems, and import them into the new collection. To date, about 40 additional STACK problems have been integrated from this second database.
- (3) Whenever there is still a gap in topical problems, identify and translate proper examples from English-language databases (e.g., the STACK quizzes based on the HELM (Helping Engineers Learn Mathematics) workbooks provided by the University of Edinburgh, cf. [Ze22]) and/or develop new STACK problems based on textbook examples or other sources. This step is currently still ongoing.
- (4) Perform initial checks of all problems for technical and didactic properties and correctness (programming, mathematical errors, correct and understandable language, etc.), and implement corrections whenever necessary. Provide solution ideas and/or full solutions to each problem if missing or incomplete. Tag all revised problems according to their contained materials (full solution, solution idea, feedback tree, etc.).⁶
- (5) On a weekly basis, add a new selection of problems matching the lecture contents of the current week as self-study material (Moodle test) to the digital mathematics learning support centre Moodle course area. Select 3-4 of them to be offered as voluntary for self-assessment (Moodle test) as part of the regular weekly practical classes of the Mathematics

⁵ During the further steps, a few more of them have been identified as topically irrelevant for the contents of our reference lectures.

⁶ This step is omitted if the contents of a given problem are not covered in the parallel course or if the full solution is too complex or requires too complicated programming work.

for Civil Engineering courses. In addition, provide another selection of 3-4 problems every 3-4 weeks for a voluntary e-assessment embedded into the lecture sessions.

(6) Collect students' feedback during/after the tutorial classes and e-assessments as well as via Moodle course logs for identifying remaining issues with the technical implementation, Moodle integration and problem formulation. Perform a second round of corrections whenever necessary. This step also involves further mutual adjustments of lecture contents and digital self-study materials to improve the cognitive alignment of the course design and materials in general.

While currently following the described workflow for the second of the three parts of the course sequence at the time of writing this report (May 2023), the topical coverage of the present state of the database (still undergoing continuous development) looks as listed below. Note that the topical areas reflect the structure of the Mathematics for Civil Engineering 1-3 course contents rather than a fully consistent organic structure of the field of Engineering Mathematics):

- Elementary mathematics (including calculations involving fractions, term manipulations, elementary geometry): 147 problems.
- Arithmetic and algebraic foundations of higher mathematics (including operations with sets, linear and nonlinear equations of various types, inequalities, complex numbers): 90 problems.
- Linear algebra (including operations with matrices and systems of linear equations): 70 problems.
- Vector algebra and analytic geometry (including operations with vectors, linear combinations, representations of and relations between points, lines, and planes in Euclidean space): 56 problems.
- Foundations of calculus (sequences and series along with their properties and convergence): 37 problems.
- Real-valued one-variable functions (including polynomials, rational, trigonometric, exponential, and logarithmic functions along with their general properties): 109 problems.
- Differential and integral calculus of real-valued one-variable functions (derivatives of functions, extreme value problems, monotonicity and curvature, Taylor series, primitive functions, and area calculations): 110 problems.
- Differential and integral calculus of real-valued multi-variable functions: 42 problems.
- Ordinary differential equations and systems thereof: 32 problems.
- Miscellaneous topics (logics, equivalence relations, applied problems, vector spaces and their bases, differential geometry) and not yet classified problems not being covered in the reference courses: 69 problems.

4 Current exploitation of mathematical STACK problems

As described above, our present exploitation scenario for the developed database of German-language mathematical STACK problems comprises two main pillars:

First, collections of STACK problems sorted by course topics that typically cover one lecture unit (90 minutes) are combined into Moodle quizzes that are freely assessable to all students at the university as part of the digital mathematics learning support centre. The collection is targeted to students that need additional digital support material for supporting the evaluation of their mathematical skills in parallel with regular undergraduate courses, as well as students requiring a refreshment of their skills at any later stage of their studies. Moreover, we provide a structured course outline for improved topical transparency and hence better synchronization between the provided contents and those of ongoing lecture series. For this purpose, the digital problems are accompanied by other digital material in written (lecture notes) and video format (links to selected external video contents). The self-study material is complemented by a weekly in-presence help session guided by one or more student assistants, where any question related to the digital material, or mathematical problems in general, can be discussed. To this end, we have encountered the problem of providing sufficient visibility to this opportunity, requiring regular advertisement via different channels (regular lectures, Moodle course, social media, etc.), without which this extra-curricular learning support centre is hardly recognized and utilized by the target group.

The second pillar consists of integrating selections of digital problems into curricular lecture series. To this end, we have started our developmental process, and henceforth also the corresponding integration, into the Mathematics for Civil Engineering courses comprising a three-semester series. Our first experiences demonstrate that the students very much appreciate the additional opportunity of digital self-assessments and use them frequently. Moreover, we have first evidence for a positive effect of the exploitation of digital mathematics problems on the results of the final written course exams [Do23].

Subsequently, we are also planning a corresponding integration into other Mathematics lecture series offered as parts of different German-language Engineering programs (Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Mechatronic Systems Technology, Water and Resource Management). At the same time, we have also recently started using weekly digital self-assessments along with regular voluntary e-assessments with English-language STACK problems in the Mathematics 1 course of our international bachelor program on Sustainable Resources, Environment & Management. For the latter purpose, we employ selected quizzes based on HELM, along with individual translations of German problems into English. Finally, we also prepare to enrich our mathematics pre-course for upcoming 1st semester students by German-language mathematical STACK problems, starting in September 2023.

5 Next steps

While the further revision and extension of the current database of STACK problems will continue until the end of the winter term 2023/24, we have already started the process of filling present topical gaps. On the one hand, we are currently integrating additional problems from the Aufgabenpool database along with translating existing English-language STACK problems from the HELM database. The latter activity is particularly affecting the currently vastly underrepresented field of statistical concepts and methods, which would also open the door to providing corresponding digital learning support and self-assessment services to other study programs in economics and the social sciences that have not been addressed by our previous efforts.

On the other hand, we are attempting to fill existing topical gaps by new STACK implementations of problems found in textbooks of Engineering Mathematics or applied fields. Here, beyond just filling topical gaps, we are planning to systematically exploit the potentials of enhanced graphical functionalities for teaching and understanding mathematics. Whenever possible, interactive graphical visualization should be integrated in the problem statements and solutions currently being developed. For this purpose, we have started exploiting the potentials of JSXGraph.

As a specific example, we are currently developing a suite of STACK problems for linear and nonlinear inequalities. Figure 1 shows a screenshot of a recently developed problem for solving a nonlinear (polynomial) inequality of the form $a \cdot x^3 + b \cdot x^2 + c \cdot x + d > 0$, where proper selections of a , b , c , and d allow for parameterization of the problem. In this example, finding the solution set potentially comprising several intervals within the real numbers is based on first finding the solution of the associated cubic equation, i.e., the roots of the cubic polynomial on the left-hand side. Instead of necessarily computing these roots explicitly, which can be somewhat challenging depending on the underlying parameter combination, we take a different avenue for solving the problem graphically. For this purpose, the graph of the function is first plotted by the system with the help of JSXGraph. Next, the user (student) is requested to identify the corresponding roots visually by identifying the roots on the graph. Finally, the associated intervals in which the inequality holds can be provided in the normal text prompt.

Bestimmen Sie die Lösungsintervalle der Ungleichung: $0.1 \cdot x^3 - 0.2 \cdot x^2 - 0.8 \cdot x > 0$

1) Geben Sie die Funktionsgleichung für $f(x)$ ein, wobei die Ungleichung $f(x) > 0$ gilt. Plotten Sie diese Funktion mit Hilfe von "Plot".

2) Verschieben Sie die gegebenen roten Punkte so, damit x_1 , x_2 und x_3 die Nullstellen der Funktion sind.

JSXGraph v12.1 Copyright (C) see <https://www.jsxgraph.org>

$f(x) = 0.1x^3 - 0.2x^2 - 0.8x$

Plot

3) Schreiben Sie die Lösungsintervalle für $f(x) > 0$ anhand des Funktionsgraphen auf.

$x \in (-\infty, -2)$

Ihre letzte Antwort wurde folgendermaßen interpretiert: $(-2, 0)$

$\cup (-\infty, 4)$

Ihre letzte Antwort wurde folgendermaßen interpretiert: $(4, \infty)$

Prüfen

Fig. 1: Example for a German-language STACK problem involving the identification of the solution set of a nonlinear (cubic) inequality enhanced by interactive graphical functionalities using JSXGraph.

Besides those topical additions, there exists vast space for further didactic improvements. One aspect to mention is the systematic extension of feedback trees to be implemented into all problems in our collection. Specifically, providing users with feedback on common misconceptions and errors might have great benefits for the learning process. To this end, we emphasize that corresponding further developments would require a lot of working time and staff commitment and might thus rather present a long-term vision than a short-term goal.

At the end of our current activities, which are currently funded until August 2024, we are planning to make the expanded and enriched database of German-language STACK problems publicly available as open educational resource.

Acknowledgements

This work has been financially supported by the Stiftung Innovation in der Hochschullehre via the project h²d².

Bibliography

- [Bo21] Bond, M.; Bedenlier, S.; Marín, V.I.; Händel, M.: Emergency remote teaching in higher education: mapping the first global online semester. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 18, 50, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00282-x>, 2021.
- [Br20] Breitschuh, C.; Eisenächer, K.; Henning, S.; Wetzel, C.: Unterstützung von Studierenden in der Studieneingangsphase – den Einstieg erleichtern, Vorkenntnisse auffrischen, Studieren lernen (in German). In: Merkt, M.; Lequy, A.; Herzog, M.A.; Ding, Y.; Wetzel, C. (Hrsg.): *Organisationsentwicklung in der Hochschullehre. Praxisberichte zum Qualitätspakt-Lehre-Projekt der Hochschule Magdeburg-Stendal*. Wby Media, Bielefeld, 17-38, 2020.
- [Do23] Donner, R.V.; Judakova, G.; Ioffe, O.B.; Brandt, K.; König, L.: Das digitale Mathematik-Lernzentrum der Hochschule Magdeburg-Stendal und seine Integration in die Grundlagen-Lehrveranstaltungen Mathematik (in German). In (Liebscher, E. et al. (eds.)): *Digitale Lehre im Rahmen der Grundlagenausbildung in MINT-Fächern an Hochschulen*. Tagungsband, Merseburg, 2023.
- [Er21] Erlam, G.D.; Garrett, N.; Gasteiger, N.; Lau, K.; Hoare, K.; Agarwal, S.; Haxell, A.: What Really Matters: Experiences of Emergency Remote Teaching in University Teaching and Learning During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Frontiers in Education*, 6, 639842, <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.639842>, 2021.
- [Ho20] Hodges, Ch.B.; Fowler, D.J.: The COVID-19 Crisis and Faculty Members in Higher Education: From Emergency Remote Teaching to Better Teaching through Reflection. In: *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Perspectives in Higher Education*, v5 n1 p118-122 2020, 2021.
- [Me14] Merkt, M.; Krauskopf, K.; Breitschuh, C.: Providing every Jack with his Jill – aiming for specific support of engineering students in developing basic mathematical skills. *Proceedings of the Conference of the International Consortium for Educational Development (ICED)*. Stockholm, Sweden, 2014.
- [Ze22] Zerva, K.; Sangwin, C.; Jones, I.; Quinn, D.: Rejuvenating the HELM Workbooks as Online STACK Quizzes in 2020. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 17 (23), 69-88, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v17i23.35923>, 2022.